

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

the article discusses modern methods of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities. The need for an innovative approach to both the content of language material and the correct choice of technologies, effective teaching methods, and control of Russian language knowledge in Uzbek groups is emphasized.

The transformation of world economic, sociocultural, political and international conditions contributes to the revision of the place of the Russian language in dialogue with other countries, and, accordingly, its promotion on the world stage. Russian is spoken by 243 million people, “more than one million study Russian in schools and universities in foreign countries and more than 12 million people in the post-Soviet space, despite the fact that Russian is considered one of the most difficult languages” [1]. Among those studying Russian both in Uzbekistan and abroad today are not only future teachers, but also future engineers, doctors, economists, translators, entrepreneurs who are mastering the Russian language as a tool for professional activity. The reason for such attention to the Russian language is not only practical interest, for example, expansion of the business space, but, above all, the desire of the world community to build harmonious relations, the need for constructive dialogue. As researcher A. Polyakova notes, “peoples today strive for rapprochement” [2].

In Uzbekistan, it is studied as a subject “Russian language” in a Russian-language school, as a subject “Russian as a foreign language” in a school with Uzbek as the language of instruction [3]. The teaching of Russian as a foreign language in the Uzbek education system is based on rich national traditions, experience, and a system of innovative methodological approaches [4]. However, today there is a need to update the methodological base at all levels - school, university, additional professional education, advanced training [5]. This is especially true for provincial universities, which in modern conditions are forced to fight for potential applicants, including foreign citizens, which will allow universities in the periphery to “take their rightful place in the international market of educational services” [6].

Currently, within the framework of teaching Russian as a foreign language or Russian language in a specialty or Russian language in non-linguistic universities, the education system of a provincial university faces the task of showing the role and place of the Russian language as a means of learning and communication in different social areas in different

interactions, such as cultural, business, socio-political, and related tasks seem to be the following:

- updating the structure and content of educational complexes in the Russian language for students at non-linguistic universities in Uzbekistan;
- creation of new approaches to organizing professionally oriented teaching of Russian as a foreign language;
- building new prospects for improving the education system in connection with the development of the global Internet;
- creation of effective optimal learning content, taking into account the specific communicative needs of students.

In addition, the urgent task of a provincial university in the existing competitive conditions is the need to improve the methodology of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities, to train qualified competitive personnel who will be able to carry out professional and pedagogical activities abroad.

The difficulty for them and for teachers lies in the difference in the level of language training. Based on personal experience, it can be noted that, despite the different levels of linguistic competence, the readiness of students at non-linguistic universities for the educational process is very high, since there is strong motivation.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY

The most important condition for the successful use of language for the purpose of communication and learning in universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan is mastery of its vocabulary, grammatical structure, written and oral forms. It is better to start teaching Russian to foreign students in an individual format [6]. "Today, there are a large number of methods and developments that are successfully used by Russian language teachers, and they are different for representatives of different nationalities, since they are based on the characteristics of the native languages of foreigners" [7].

An important component in the educational process is cognitive interest, which is the fundamental motivation for active student activity. Interest in the subject helps you better understand the material. Today, the main task of training is not only the transfer of certain knowledge and skills, but also the formation of personal and professionally significant qualities in the student. This problem is solved by innovative approaches to teaching, shifting

the emphasis from the activity of the teacher to the activity of the students.

It is known that difficulties in learning a new language are associated with the student's adaptation to another culture, customs, traditions, history, and values of another people. Therefore, for the effective development of speech in a non-native language, methods are needed that promote the acquisition of skills in conversation, reading and translation [1]. We see a solution in the use of innovative approaches to developing methods of teaching the Russian language for Uzbek students.

To express thoughts in a non-native language, knowledge of the rules alone is not enough; first of all, it is necessary to expand the vocabulary. To do this, even at the stage of familiarization with new texts, we use exercises that involve making guesses about the content of the text based on the context of the keywords. We analyze syntactic structures, identify characteristic Russian vocabulary, and study the context of the use of keywords.

Students perceive the rules of the Russian language through the grammar of their native language, which is the cause of interference errors in spelling and punctuation. The development of a methodology for teaching the Russian language with an emphasis on typical mistakes typical for students speaking the Uzbek language made it possible to accelerate the process of mastering language material.

In the process of learning the Russian language, working with a dictionary is important. Effective techniques in Russian language classes were simultaneous translations from Russian into Uzbek and vice versa, building an associative series, graphic representation of a word, and the use of other mnemonics. An effective approach to teaching methods is to work in groups in pairs, which allows you to create various speech situations. For the full implementation of communicative competence, native speakers of the Russian language are involved.

Currently, information and computer technologies are widely used in the study of foreign languages. They contribute to the development of students' independence in the process of learning language material. With the help of training programs and applications, you can expand the boundaries of knowledge, create new methods and methods of self-learning and self-realization. In addition, the implementation of computerized knowledge testing helps to implement the principle of individualization of education [2]. During Russian language classes we conduct media lessons. Such classes arouse the interest of students, allow them to focus their attention on the right moments, stimulate activity, and reveal creative abilities. An interesting activity contributes to faster and easier learning of language material. Internet tests are also conducted both to test students' knowledge on specific topics, and to identify existing gaps in material studied long ago, and self-assessment of abilities.

To summarize, we can conclude that the use of innovative technologies in practical classes of the Russian language in groups with Uzbek language of instruction helps to improve communication skills. In addition, the use of modern technologies motivates teachers to introduce new methods into the educational process.

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